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Research Article

Phytochemical Screening and Biological Evaluation OF *Daucus Carota* Root & Stem Extracts

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ABSTRACT

The present work to evaluate the phytochemical screening and biological evaluation of *Daucus carota* root and stem extracts. we done screening for antimitotic and antibacterial activities. The extracts of this plant also found applications in many of the traditional medicines. The antibacterial activities were assay of organic extract of *Daucus carota* root & stem. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) were evaluated using standard microbiological techniques. They showed a high significant antibacterial activity using microorganisms such as *Bacillus* sp., *staphylococcus* sp. *lactobascillus*, *Xanthomonas*. Appreciable quantities of phytochemical such as alkaloids, glycosides, phytobatanins proteins and amino acids.

INTRODUCTION

Daucus carota having a scientific name of carrot belongs to family apiaceae and it contains many of chemical constituent. The carrot (*Daucus carota* subsp. *sativus*) is a root vegetable, usually orange in colour, but many other were found like purple, black, red, white and yellow varieties exist. Aromatic and medicinal plants, have been widely used in folk medicine to treat several ailments. Which are widely described as having several

bioactive properties such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, antibacterial, hepatoprotective, cardioprotective, anti-hypertensive, antidiabetic, immune enhancer activity, wound healing activity [1-13]. The species *Daucus carota* commonly known as carrot, is recognized worldwide due roots widely used for both food and medicinal purposes. It is one of the edible root plants and a rich source of anthocyanins, carotenoids (α , β , λ carotene), vitamins A, B and C.

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Table 1: Taxonomical Classification [14]

Kingdom	Plantae
Subkingdom	Tracheophyta
Superdivision	Spermatophyta
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Apiales
Family	Apiaceae
Genus	<i>Daucus</i>
Species	<i>Carota</i>
subspecies	<i>Sativus</i>

Figure.1: Cultivation, Isolation, Separation, Size Reduction, Preparation *Daucus Carota* Root Extract

Table.2: Test and procedures for Phytochemical Screening [15,16]

S. No	Test for Phytochemicals	Procedure
1	Alkaloids	<p>Dragendroff's Test</p> <p>1g of the formulation was extracted with 20 ml alcohol by refluxing for 15 min and filtered and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in 15 ml of 2N H₂SO₄ and filtered. Filtrate was made alkaline and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was evaporated to dryness on the water bath. The residue left after evaporation was tested for the presence of alkaloids</p>

			with dragendroff's reagent. Formation of orange-coloured precipitates indicates the presence of alkaloids.
2	Carbohydrates	Molisch's Test	To the ethanolic extracts of formulations, α -naphthol and concentrated H ₂ SO ₄ were added. Development of purple colored ring indicates the presence of carbohydrates.
		Fehling's Test	To 1 ml of ethanolic extracts of formulations, 1 ml of the Fehling solution (Fehling A + Fehling B) was added. The mixture was heated on boiling water bath for 5-10 min. Development of yellow precipitates, changing to brick red precipitates indicates the presence of reducing sugars.
3	Glycosides	Chrysoarobin Test	0.1 gm of powder was dissolved in H ₂ SO ₄ , deep red solution is produced indicates the presence of glycosides.
4	Flavonoids	FeCl ₃ Test	Extract was treated with FeCl ₃ solution. Formation of green to black color indicates presence of flavonoids.
		Shinoda Test	Extract was treated with the mixture containing piece of magnesium ribbon and HCl. Formation of red colour indicates presence of flavonoids.
		NaOH Test	To the extract add 10% NaOH was added, Formation of yellow colour indicates presence of flavonoids.
		Lead acetate Test	To the extract add 10% Lead acetate solution was added. Formation of yellow colour ppt. indicates presence of flavonoids.
		Mineral acid Test	To the drug add conc. H ₂ SO ₄ was added. Formation of orange colour indicates presence of flavonoids.
		Zn/HCl Test	Pinch of zinc dust was added to extract and conc. HCl was added. Formation of red colour indicates presence of flavonoids.
6	Tannins	Lead acetate Test	To 2-3 ml of aqueous extracts of the formulations, 2 ml of 10 % w/w solution of lead acetate was added. Formation of heavy dull yellowish precipitates indicates the presence of tannins.
7	Proteins	Biuret Test	To 3 ml of extracts of the formulations, add 4% NaOH and few drops of 1% CuSO ₄ solution. Violet or pink colour appears.
		Millon's Test	To 3 ml of extracts of the formulations, add 5ml Millon's reagent. White precipitate is formed. Upon warming, the precipitate turns brick red or the precipitate dissolves giving red coloured solution.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collection and identification of plant material:

Daucus carota plant consists root, flowers, stem, etc. The long and short leaves were procured from the backyard of state bank of India, Dallavalasa

village ponduru mandal, Srikakulam, Andhra Pradesh state of India.

Preparation of *Daucus carota* root extract:

Root part was isolated from the *Daucus carota* and then cut it into small pieces i.e in 2.5cms and make into extract this extract is directly used to carry out the biological activities and phytochemical screening studies.

Phytochemical Screening.

Phytochemical screening of extracts

Following chemical tests were carried out for *Daucus carota* root extract to identify the presence of various phytochemical constituents. Chemical tests for detection of chemical constituents:

Table.3: Phytochemical Screening of *Daucus carota* root Extract

S.no	Tests	Results
1	Alkaloids	+
2	Glycosides	+
3	Tannins	+
4	Proteins	+
5	Amino Acids	+

According to this report of *Daucus carota* root Extract showed the presence of alkaloids, glycosides, tannins, proteins and Amino acids.

Evaluation of Antimitotic activity of *Daucus carota* root extract [17]

Green gram seeds were purchased from the market and stored in a moisture free place in self-sealing cover. Then accurately weighed 5grams of seeds and incorporated in each and every sigma-aldrich polystyrene petri dishes to study the antimitotic activity of *Daucus carota* root extract. In Control only vehicle is used that vehicle is distilled water. After getting the results of antimitotic activity of root extract of *daucus carota*. we randomly selected 3 seeds from each and every petriplate and calculate the germination length in cms of the seeds and after that we done average length calculation.

Table.4: Preparation of Antimitotic activity of *Daucus carota* root extract.

S.no	Concentration of <i>Daucus carota</i> root extract (ml)	Contents in the petriplate
1	Control (0ml Extract)	10ml vehicle only
2	0.5ml Extract	10ml vehicle + 0.5ml Extract
3	1ml Extract	10mlvehicle+1ml Extract
4	1.5ml Extract	10mlvehicle+1.5ml Extract
5	2ml Extract	10mlvehicle+2ml Extract

Figure.2: Antimitotic Activity of *Daucus Carota* Root Extract

Table.5: Result of Antimitotic activity of *Daucus carota* root extract.

S. No	Concentration of <i>Daucus carota</i> root extract (ML)	Length of seeds (cm)	Average length of the seeds(cm)
1	Control	First Seed- 2.7cm Second seed -2cm Third seed -2cm	$2.7+2+2 = 6.7/3$ =2.3cms
2	0.5ml	First Seed- 1.9cm Second seed-1.5cm Third seed -1.5cm	$1.9+1.5+1.5 = 4.9/3$ = 1.63cms
3	1ml	First seed -1.5cm Second seed-1cm Third seed-1cm	$1.5+1+1 = 3.5/3$ =1.16cms
4	1.5ml	First seed -1cm Second seed -1.6cm Third seed -1.8cm	$1+1.6+1.8 = 2.2/3$ = 0.733cms
5	2ml	First seed -0cm Second seed -0cm Third seed -0cm	No germination of seeds

From the results of antimitotic activity of *Daucus carota* root extract we conclude that highest strength of the extract is not having any seed

germination.so this root extract is having potential antimitotic activity.

Figure.3: Graphical representation of Antimitotic activities of *Daucus carota* root extract

Evaluation of Anti-microbial activity of *Daucus carota* root extract [18]

We collect sugarcane stem from the sugarcane field at Dharma puram village, Ponduru mandal, Srikakulam, Andhra Pradesh State. From that we cut sugarcane stem into small pieces these pieces were going to be crushed then finally we get a sugarcane solution, from that we filtered it thus we obtained sugarcane filtrate. Immediately after sugarcane is cut, the microflora inside its stem is composed of yeasts and bacteria. Bacteria like *Bacillus sp.*, *Staphylococcus sp.*, *Lactobacillus*, *Xanthomonas*. So this sugarcane filtrate is used as

nutrient medium and as well as bacterial culture. Firstly the sugarcane filtrate nutrient media 2ml was added to all test tubes. Then after add different concentration like 0.5ml, 1ml, 1.5ml and 2ml of *Daucus carota* Root extract, For this we use levofloxacin antibiotic pure API and kept for incubation for 24 hours.

Preparation of Levofloxacin drug solution:

Accurately weigh about 1gm of pure levofloxacin drug and dissolved in the distilled water then make up to 50ml with the distilled water in the Volumetric flask.

Figure.4: Results of Antimicrobial Activities with *Daucus carota* root extract.

From the Figure.4: antibacterial activity of *Daucus carota* root extract. We conclude that highest concentration of this extract is show more bacterial killing capability by visual conformation forming

high quantity of Turbidity that is compared with the standard drug levofloxacin.so this root extract is having potential antibacterial activity.

Figure.5: Cultivation, isolation, size reduction & preparation of stem extract of *Daucus carota*

Table.7: Phytochemical Screening Data of *Daucus carota* Stem extract [15,16]

S.no.	Phytochemical Constituents	Result
1.	Alkaloids	+
2.	Flavanoids	+
3.	Tannins	+
4.	Saponins	+
5.	Terpenoids	+
6.	Glycosides	+
7.	Coumarins	+

8.	Phenols	+
9.	Protiens	+
10.	Reducing Sugars	+

According to this report of *Daucus carota* stem Extract showed the presence of alkaloids, flavanoids, tannins, saponins, terpenoids, glycosides, coumarins, phenols, proteins, reducing sugars.

Evaluation of Antimitotic activity of *Daucus carota* stem extract.[17]

Black gram seeds were purchased from the market and stored in a moisture free place in self-sealing cover. Then accurately weighed 5grams of seeds and incorporated in each and every sigma-aldrich polystyrene petri dishes to study the antimutic activity of *Daucus carota* root extract. In Control only vehicle is used that vehicle is distilled water. After getting the results of antimutic activity of stem extract of *Daucus carota*. we randomly selected 3 seeds from each and every sigma-aldrich polystyrene petri dishes and calculate the germination length in cms of the seeds and after that we done average length calculation.

Table.8: Preparation of Antimutic activity of *Daucus carota* stem extract.

S.no	Concentration of <i>Daucus carota</i> Stem extract (ml)	Contents in the petriplate
1	Control (0ml Extract)	10ml vehicle only
2	0.5ml Extract	10ml vehicle + 0.5ml Extract
3	1ml Extract	10mlvehicle+1ml Extract
4	1.5ml Extract	10mlvehicle+1.5ml Extract
5	2ml Extract	10mlvehicle+2ml Extract

Figure.6: Antimutic activity of *Daucus carota* stem extract

Table.9: Result of Antimutic activity of *Daucus carota* stem extract

S. No	Concentration of <i>Daucus carota</i> stem extract (ml)	Length of seeds (cm)	Average length of the seeds (cms)
1	Control	First Seed -1.3cms Second seed -1.7cms Third seed -1.3cms	$1.3+1.7+1.3 = 4.3/3 = 1.43cms$

2	0.5ml	First Seed- 1.8cm Second seed-2cm Third seed -2.4cm	$1.8+2+2.4 = 6.2/3$ $= 2.06\text{cms}$
3	1ml	First seed -2.3cm Second seed-1.5cm Third seed-1.6cm	$2.3+1.5+1.6 = 5.4/3$ $=1.8\text{cms}$
4	1.5ml	First seed -1cm Second seed -1.5cm Third seed -0.8cm	$1+1.5+0.8 = 3.3/3$ $= 1.1\text{cms}$
5	2ml	First seed -0.9cm Second seed -0.6cm Third seed -0.4cm	$0.9+0.6+0.4 = 1.9/3$ $=0.63\text{cms}$

From the results of antimutic activity of *Daucus carota* stem. When compared to the remaining strength of *Daucus carota* stem extract there is

gradually decreased in the seed germination is noticed.so this stem extract is having appreciable antimutic activity.

Figure.7: Graphical representation of antimutic activity of *Daucus carota* stem extract

Evaluation of Anti-microbial activity of *Daucus carota* stem extract [18]

Sugarcane stem is into small pieces these pieces was going to crushed then finally we get a sugarcane solution, from that we filtered it thus we obtained sugarcane filtrate. Immediately after sugarcane is cut, the microflora inside its stem is composed of yeasts and bacteria. Bacteria like *bacillus sp.*, *staphylococcus sp.*, *lactobascillus*, *xanthomonas*. So this sugarcane filtrate is used as nutrient medium and as well as bacterial culture. Firstly the curd filtrate nutrient media 2ml was added to all test tubes. Then after add different concentration like 0.5ml,1ml, 1.5ml and 2ml of

Daucus carota stem extract, for this we use Gentamicin antibiotic pure API and kept for incubation for 24hours and results was observed.

Preparation of Gentamicin drug solution

Accurately weight about 1gm of pure Gentamicin drug and dissolved in the distilled water then make up to 50ml with the distilled water in the Volumetric flask.

Table.10: Preparation of Antibacterial Activity of *Daucus carota* stem extract.

S.no	Test tubes	Contents in the Test tubes
1	Test tube-1 (control)	2ml filtrate + Gentamicin drug(1.5ml)
2	Test tube-2	2ml filtrate + 0.5ml stem extract of <i>Daucus carota</i>

3	Test tube-3	2ml filtrate + 1ml stem extract of <i>Daucus carota</i>
4	Test tube-4	2ml filtrate + 1.5ml stem extract of <i>Daucus carota</i>
5	Test tube-5	2ml filtrate + 2ml stem extract of <i>Daucus carota</i>

Figure.8: Results of Antimicrobial Activities with *Daucus carota* stem extract

From the Figure.8: antibacterial activity of *Daucus carota* stem extract. We conclude that highest concentration of this extract is show more bacterial killing capability by visual conformation forming high quantity of Turbidity that is compared with the standard drug gentamicin.so this root extract is having potential antibacterial activity.

CONCLUSION:

The present work was carried out to investigate the antimicrobial activity and phytochemical screening of *Daucus carota* root and stem extracts. First the *Daucus carota* root and stem extracts was prepared as per the standard procedure. Results demonstrated that, the extract of *Daucus carota* root shows the presence of Photochemical like Alkaloids, glycosides, tannins,

proteins and amino acids. *Daucus carota* stem extract showed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, terpenoids, glycosides, coumarins, phenols, proteins, reducing sugars. Antimicrobial property of *Daucus carota* root extract was revealed. The result shows that the highest concentration of *Daucus carota* root extract sample exhibits potent antimicrobial activity. The sample possess good antimicrobial activity at their highest strength. Stem extract of *Daucus carota* also show both antimicrobial and antibacterial activity. Finally, it is concluded that the *Daucus carota* root extract exhibited high potential antimicrobial and antimicrobial activities when compared to stem extracts of *Daucus carota*.

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